

PHOTO-REALISTIC WEATHER VISUALIZATION USING REMOTELY SENSED SATELLITE IMAGERY AND METEOROLOGICAL COLLATERAL DATA

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ABSTRACT:

Existing weather visualization techniques are found deficient when it is required to show those characteristics of hurricanes/storms that can help weather forecasters predict whether a cloud cover is going to turn into a thunderstorm/tornado. Can a visualization of weather model data provide enough visual cues to make a timely and accurate prediction? In this project, we have tried to combine weather datasets that have been generated in laboratories with remotely sensed data in a Geographical Information Systems environment. We thus plan to implement visualization exercises aimed at realizing the extensive meteorological data associated with storms and hurricanes into easily interpretable photo realistic images, which can then be used for analysis and assessment by weather forecasters. Conclusions would be drawn from the developed visual images on expected precipitation, estimated flooding and related damage based on the intensity of the hurricane/storm and its related meteorological phenomena including pressure distribution through contouring, intensity of the cloud cover, water vapor content of the atmosphere and its distribution, temperature and humidity changes etc. Finally a predictive study will be proposed where in the current information could be used as a means to estimate the intensity and effects of similar hurricanes/storms that occur at various other places. A suggestive inference could then be drawn on the preparation and precautionary measures that need to be taken to counter to a certain extent the devastating nature of such weather phenomena to limit the extent of loss and damage to a minimum and prevent such natural activities turning into large scale calamities.

I. INTRODUCTION:

Simulation of data-sets into visual patterns provides for a better understanding of the data as human perception is enhanced. Weather forecasting is important for a host of activities. Government authorities require precise and timely information to limit the damage from catastrophic meteorological events such as extreme high tides or hurricanes. Military decisions rely on these for strategic reasons and the technical community apart from the lay man is also a very interested audience. Visualization has been crudely defined as the transformation of data or information into pictures. The result is a simple and effective medium for communicating complex and or voluminous information [1]. A refined definition calls visualization as a method of computing by which the strength and the processing power of the human visual (eye-brain) system becomes an integral part of extracting knowledge from complex data [1]. The effectiveness of visualization will be defined by how well user goals are met. It can be used for analysis in decision making and or in presentations to share results.

Remote sensing on the other hand has been conceptualized as the science and art of obtaining information about an object, area or phenomenon through the analysis of data acquired by a device that is not in contact with the object, area or phenomenon [2]. The data collected may be spatial, spectral or temporal in nature and the features thus established may be represented in the image space, feature space or the signal space. GIS or geographic information systems which is the other tool that has been extensively used in this study has been defined as a powerful set of tools for collecting, storing, retrieving at will, transforming and displaying spatial data from the real world for a particular set of purposes. The geographical data represents phenomena from the real world in terms of their position with respect to a coordinate system, their attributes that are unrelated to the position and their spatial inter-relations with each other often described as the topology [3]. While this is a tool-box based definition other popular definitions of GIS include data base definitions and organization based definitions. The former describes GIS as a spatially indexed query supporting data base system while the latter defines GIS as a decision support system with an automated set of functions in a spatial problem solving environment [3].

II. PREVIOUS WORK:

Visualization in meteorology has been a feature even before computing power become available easily when meteorologists drew contour maps of weather data by hand from observations to communicate a forecast. Numerical models were then used to develop scientific applications of computer systems, and the creation of computer-generated two-dimensional graphical representations of weather data was among the first applications of visualization. Geographical Information Systems are now being used to visualize data when ever it has a spatial attribute. In Serbia, a GIS based Hail Suppression Information System (HASIS) exists, detecting Cumulo Nimbus clouds, which causes hail, when certain parameters such as height above the ground, temperature etc are satisfied [5]. Visualization is done so that the extracted data from a radar echo can be easily detected and used. The visualization system needs to allow even the layman users to understand what the weather has in store [6].

The authors, *Ding, Jie and Aoki, Yoshinao* [7] in their study concentrated their work in developing an interactive system for efficiently processing remote sensing meteorological data. The system was designed to focus primarily on scientific visualization of radar reflectivity intensity data, which we understand as the spectral signatures of the cloud cover and other atmospheric features and the compression of satellite cloud picture.

The objective of such a system as discussed by the authors is to visualize into a color map the reflective intensity numerical data in real time and accompanying satellite cloud picture fractal image compression can help draw meaningful weather information. The visualization process of reflectivity involves reading the observing time, dividing the data into parts and then visualizing the reflectivity into a functional RGB color model map. The satellite cloud picture work included developing an encoder and decoder to compress and decompress vast data for easier and faster transmission and storage.

A useful research proposes a satellite image based modeling of realistically created clouds using metaballs [8]. Among the various intentions of the research, the most relevant include the visualization of weather information and the simulation of the surveys of the earth. The exercise aims to use the various parameters of a metaball including center positions, radii and density values to determine a synthesized image of clouds that is similar to the original satellite image. An animation of the simulated clouds was also proposed. Also task specific weather visualization software can provide huge amount of help when such the need arises [9]. Such a system should also use meteorological parameters to predict rapid weather changes.

Further research by *Lakshmanan, V; Vaughan, Thomas* [10] talks about how to obtain and optimally visualize weather data from multiple sources in an integrated manner. The time variant data was geographically and temporally referenced and the study aimed at perfecting a system whose design capability was to thus provide a real time or play back means of accessing data from disparate sources for a common weather information algorithm and visualization development.

The paper describes the various data formats, the methodologies used for data fusion, time synchronization amongst different data sets and other such exercises before the actual batch visualization. Data representation was carried out by referencing the data to a pre-determined earth fixed spherical coordinate system or an earth fixed cartesian coordinate frame. The data was then modeled in the 4D space with the three coordinates and the temporal one being the four dimensions. An algorithm driven oct-tree visualization that concentrated on time synchronization of different data sets and multiple image data integration aspects was then implemented. Volume rendering and flow visualization tasks ensured attractive presentation capability to the study.

The authors, *Tian-yue Jiang, William Ribarsky, Tony Wasilewski, Nickolas Faust, Brendan Hannigan and Mitchell Parry* [11] in their paper discuss the visualization of real time Doppler radar data over high-resolution global terrain data. They have presented methods for real-time acquisition, organization, and visualization of atmospheric data in a geospatial environment, emphasizing capabilities that will be of use to forecasters and other decision-makers. The paper also discusses and gives a list of previous work that has been done which helped us in our search for related materials. The authors list some of the requirements

from a visualization system, including effective visualization for decision-making, End-to-end real-time capability, i.e. not just visualization but also on-the-spot analysis in appropriate time budgets. They also discuss the importance of a priori data for prediction and how signatures of tornadoes can be obtained more easily if previous tornadoes are studied along with their parameters.

Work by *Thomas Gerstner, Dirk Meetschen, Susanne Crewell, Michael Griebel, Clemens Simmer* [12] talks about using three-dimensional radar scan data and 2D terrain data to create interactive visualization of the data sets. The paper gives a good overview of the data sets involved and the methods of collecting and processing the required data. The authors then visualize terrain as in 2D and the radar data in 3D. The 3D visualization, called Rain field Visualization by the authors requires volume rendering and/or iso-surface extraction. In this paper, the authors extract multiple transparent iso-surfaces. Combining with collateral meteorological data, the authors use volume visualization of rainfall measurements from a radar dataset.

III. DATASETS:

Datasets representing various meteorological phenomena such as cloud, rain, ice, snow and graup* were collected. The data were in 3D unsigned binary .raw files with dimensions of 128x64x128.

Fig 1: Unrefined visualization model for “snow” data

The visualization obtained from the examples basically show snow simulations done in laboratory. Remotely Sensed datasets and collateral information such as Humidity, Temperature and Rainfall data were obtained from the National Oceanic & Atmospheric Administration web page (www.noaa.gov). The remote sensing data is in the form of RGB multi-spectral and gray tone infra red images.

* Graup as defined by the meteorological community, refers to soft hail

Fig 2: Multi-spectral RGB image of a hurricane formation over the south Pacific close to the Hawaiian islands**

IV. PROCEDURE:

To integrate the simulated dataset with remotely sensed satellite data and other collateral information, we need a tool that can handle all or at least most of these types of data. A Geographic Information System is just such a kind of tool. Its organized collection of computer hardware, software, geographic data, and personnel designed to efficiently capture, store, update, manipulate, analyze, and display all forms of geographically (spatially) referenced information is effectively used in this study.

Data from the datasets obtained from the Center for Analysis and Prediction of Storms (CAPS) at the University of Oklahoma, was initially analyzed using IBM Open DX***. It basically represents the intensity of a given geophysical phenomenon (snow, ice, cloud etc).

For most applications of Remote Sensing data, it needs to be geo-referenced and geo-coded. This was accomplished using ESRI's Arc/View GIS software. First, the political boundaries of all the states of mainland and other parts of USA including Alaska and Hawaii, were digitized. The remote sensing image was converted to the required coordinate system using affine transformation. Thus the dataset was geo-registered to a common referencing system.

Image Transformation

The image-to-world transformation is a six-parameter affine transformation in the form of:

$$x_1 = A*x + B*y + C$$

$$y_1 = D*x + E*y + F$$

where

** Courtesy: NOAA satellite image archive

*** data visualization software developed by IBM Inc

x_1 = calculated x-coordinate of the pixel on the map
 y_1 = calculated y-coordinate of the pixel on the map
 x = column number of a pixel in the image
 y = row number of a pixel in the image

A = x-scale; dimension of a pixel in map units in x direction
B, D = rotation terms
C, F = translation terms; (x, y) map coordinates of the center of the upper-left pixel
E = negative of y-scale; dimension of a pixel in map units in y direction

Coordinates of the same points (at least 3) were collected from the map as well as the imagery and then plugged in to the equations to get the required parameters (for more than 3 points, a least squares solution was determined). This step was accomplished using Matlab and the values of the parameters were thus obtained and recorded.

Fig 3: World file

The first row in the screen capture seen above is the X scale factor, the next two rows are the rotation elements, the fourth row is a negative Y scale factor (because of the left handed coordinate system) and the final two rows give the shifts necessary to bring the image into the required precise location.

The screen shot shows what ArcView calls a “World File” which stores the header information of the image to get it into the correct coordinate system.

Then both the remote sensing data and the datasets obtained from CAPS were analyzed using the Matlab programming environment. The RS data was converted from a 2D dataset to a 128X64X128 array and each array was given a value proportional to that obtained from the CAPS data. Then the intensity value at that location was interpolated using a linear interpolation method via a Matlab function called GridData3 ().

Using this, areas of cloud were classified into various regions such that these regions represent areas where you can expect high or low rainfall, as the case may be. A contour map of the intensity values was also created giving each pixel a different elevation value. The idea was that areas where the clouds were at a higher elevation and at the same time have a height intensity value can expect higher rainfall.

This combined dataset was then saved in a binary format and visualized in IBM-Open DX. The following are some of the visualizations:

Fig 7: Sample visualization of the multi-spectral Image

Fig 8: Another sample visualization of the multi-spectral image

The intensity of the cloud over an area can be interpreted from the color. Then the collateral meteorological data was visualized for the state of Indiana. Data regarding rainfall temperature and humidity was collected for all the major cities of Indiana. A grid representing Indiana (128X64) was created and the pixels corresponding to the positions of the cities were given attributes for rainfall, temperature and humidity. Then the data was interpolated to all the pixels using bilinear interpolation. Thus a 3D grid was generated by converting this 2D array to a 3D one and giving values for each cell in the Z dimension based on the interpolated values of the base pixels. This data was then visualized using IBM Open DX.

Fig 9: Humidity distribution for Indiana

Fig 10: Temperature distribution for Indiana

This data can be integrated within a GIS such that they are overlaid with the vector maps for the area and the true aerial extents of the various meteorological phenomena can be seen.

Fig 11: Extent of cloud cover

Fig 12: Contour map of the region

V. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS:

Using the combined visualizations from the different datasets, it might be easier to decide the weather pattern for an area and also for predicting the short term weather changes. GIS can also be used as an effective data retrieval system such that meteorological data for any part of the study area can be determined by just clicking on the area. An illustration of such an interactive user friendly system is given below. Apart from being interactive the system thus designed is also real time and requires no technical expertise to derive the requisite weather information and forecasts or the necessary meteorological and geophysical parameters for the more eager and trained population.

Fig 13: Sample data base and spatial join

Further visualization exercises help reduce the computational complexity in understanding and interpreting the extensive meteorological parameters and provides for a faster, accurate and reliable decision making process apart from referencing itself for future research work. Real time high accuracy visualization also helps in achieving conclusive results from the analysis of geophysical parameters.

In summary, the project could not be completed to the desired extent as specified by the guidelines in the abstract due to paucity of time and resources. In lieu of the abstract the conclusions from the visual images with regards to expected precipitation, estimated flooding and related damage were not obtained. Also various other meteorological phenomena like pressure and temperature distribution could not be mapped. This led to the absence of a well defined predictive data model being developed. However as suggested in the future work section, an extensive further study is planned and will be conducted for realizing a thorough visualization of the above data set with complete quantitative estimation of the related parameters.

VI. FUTURE WORK:

A good follow on the project would be to come up with extensive quantitative estimation of the meteorological parameters that would lead to a better understanding of the physical significance of the parameters defined. This estimation thus would lead to the development of an accurate weather prediction model that could well be referenced for future research and use. A mathematical linear or polynomial regression model for quantifying the relationships between various independent, correlated and uncorrelated parameters with the dependant or unknown parameters will be the final goal of this study. Future referencing can also be achieved through the generation of a processed and visualized data archive. Further work has been envisaged in designing a methodology for simulating missing data when required given the conditions prevailing prior to and after the corresponding phenomena has occurred. Statistical predictive tools, mathematical interpolation techniques and data fitting exercises will be explored in detail in this regard. Finally it is proposed to incorporate the technique of fly-by visualization and animation of the end results to enhance the interpretability and present ability of the study. Use of visualization techniques in combination with machine learning, data mining and knowledge discovery that incorporate the processes of active learning and feature selection will also be an ideal area to further extend this study.

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